

according to which

$$k_{t,th}^0 = \frac{kT}{h} \phi \exp \left[\frac{-\Delta G}{RT} \right] \quad (3)$$

Where k = Boltzmann constant, h = Plank's constant, $\phi = 2.0 \times 10^{-8}$ cm and other terms have their usual significance. From the equation (3), the values of ΔG for Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} systems are found to be 12.39 and 6.51 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively.

The entropy of activation (ΔS) calculated from the relation $\Delta S = (\Delta H - \Delta G)/T$, are found to be -146.15 and -28.37 cal mol⁻¹ deg⁻¹ for Zn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} , respectively.

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Hydrolysis of Esters in Slurry Phase Over Zinc Oxide Catalysts

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ESTER hydrolysis in heterogeneous systems using ion-exchange resins and mixed oxide catalysts are well known¹⁻⁴. Zinc oxide has been reported to be effective in splitting oils and fats⁵⁻⁷ in the preparation of fatty acids. This communication reports the kinetics of hydrolysis of aliphatic and aromatic esters over zinc oxide in slurry phase by conductivity method. The hydrolysis follows first order kinetics. Thermodynamic parameters are calculated for these reactions.

Experimental

Methyl acetate, ethyl acetate and methyl benzoate (A.R., B.D.H.) were purified by standard procedure⁸ and their purity was checked by gas chromatography.

Catalyst A (ZnO) was prepared by adding ammonium hydroxide (A.R., B.D.H.) to a boiling zinc nitrate solution and the resulting zinc hydroxide precipitate was washed thoroughly and dried in an air oven at 120° for 12 h and then decomposed in a muffle furnace at 400° for 24 h. Catalyst B was obtained by the decomposition of zinc carbonate (A.R., B.D.H.) at 400° in a muffle furnace. Catalyst C was a commercial grade ZnO (B.D.H.). All samples were powdered and sieved to different mesh size and activated at 700° for 6 h by passing pure dry air through the sample and were cooled and preserved in a vacuum desiccator.

Procedure: 100 ml ester solution of known concentration was transferred into a 150 ml wide-mouthed bottle and a dip type conductivity cell was inserted into the solution. The arrangement was thermostated and kept over a magnetic platform. At the desired temperature known quantity of zinc oxide (100-120 mesh) was added to the system and the content stirred. Initial resistance (R_0), change in resistance at time t , (R_t) and at infinite reading (R_∞) after 24 h were measured. The corresponding conductance values are σ_0 , σ_t and σ_∞ . Initial ester concentration is equivalent to $(\sigma_\infty - \sigma_0)$. Amount of ester hydrolysed or amount of acid formed is equivalent to $(\sigma_t - \sigma_0)$. Ester concentration at time t is equivalent to $(\sigma_\infty - \sigma_t)$. After each experiment the catalyst was filtered, washed, dried and activated at 500° for 6 h by passing pure dry air.

Results and Discussion

The resistance remained constant with time when the experiment was performed (i) without ester, and (ii) without catalyst. In order to check the possibility of dissolution of the catalyst in water, the former was added to the latter, stirred for 1 h and filtered. No hydrolysis was observed when ester was added to the filtrate.

The resistance of acetic acid solution of known concentration remained constant before and after the addition of zinc oxide. This ensures that the observed resistance was only due to liberated acetic acid during hydrolysis and not due to the zinc acetate formation.

The effect of stirrer speed on the reaction rate was studied and the rate was found to be independent above 200 rpm. Since the kinetic studies were made at a stirrer speed of above 200 rpm, it is assumed that there is no diffusional effect.

The influence of particle size of catalysts A, B and C on the hydrolysis of methyl acetate was studied and the data are given in Table 1. Decrease

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF PARTICLE SIZE ON RATE CONSTANT

Catalyst	Rate constant; $k \times 10^3, \text{min}^{-1}$			
	100-120 mesh	72-100 mesh	52-72 mesh	36-52 mesh
A	3.428	2.572	1.687	1.213
B	2.558	1.863	1.186	0.928
C	1.740	1.142	0.895	0.552

in catalyst particle size results in an increase in the rate of hydrolysis. From these values, the activity of the catalysts is found to be in the following order: catalyst A > catalyst B > catalyst C.

The initial rates were obtained from Fig. 1 and from a log-log plot of initial rate vs initial concentration of methyl acetate (Fig. 2) the order of

Fig. 1. Liberation of acetic acid from methyl acetate with time at 29° over catalyst A. A=0.378; B=0.63; C=0.881; and D=1.133 M.

Fig. 2. Plot of log (initial rate) vs log (initial concentration) for methyl acetate. Temp. 29°.

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log(\sigma_\alpha - \sigma_t)$ vs time at 29° for methyl acetate over catalyst A. A=0.1; B=0.2; C=0.3; D=0.5; E=0.75; F=1.0; and G=1.5 g.

Fig. 4. Effect of catalyst concentration on rate constant for catalyst A at 29°. A=methyl acetate (0.503 M); B=ethyl acetate (0.5108 M); and methyl benzoate (0.56 M).

reaction was found to be 1.034. From the slopes of the plot (Fig. 3), the rate constants were calculated for methyl acetate over different amounts of catalyst A. Effect of catalyst concentration on rate constant for the three esters over catalyst A is shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the rate of

hydrolysis is in the following order : methyl acetate > ethyl acetate > methyl benzoate. The increase in the rate constant upto about 1.0 g (Fig. 4) may probably be due to the complete and uniform dispersion of the catalyst in the reaction vessel. Further additions beyond 1.0 g increase the bulk of the catalyst, but the ester molecules may not be able to reach the interior of the catalyst bulk and get adsorbed over the catalyst. Hence, the rates begin to fall.

The activation energy (E_a), frequency factor (PZ) and thermodynamic parameters (ΔG^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger) for the three systems were calculated using Arrhenius and Eyring's equation⁹ and the values are given in Table 2. The higher value of activation

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS, FREQUENCY FACTOR AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDROLYSIS OF METHYL ACETATE, ETHYL ACETATE AND METHYL BENZOATE OVER CATALYST A

Temp. K	$k \times 10^4$, sec ⁻¹	PZ $\times 10^{-3}$, sec ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger , kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger , kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger , JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Methyl Acetate $E_a = 44.18$ kJ mol ⁻¹					
302.0	5.746	2.514	41.672	98.540	-188.20
308.0	8.064	2.506	41.623	99.669	-188.50
314.0	11.171	2.494	41.579	100.800	-188.70
Ethyl Acetate $E_a = 52.42$ kJ mol ⁻¹					
309.5	8.090	82.45	49.901	100.60	-167.00
311.5	5.118	81.49	49.834	102.01	-167.50
319.5	8.251	80.63	49.567	103.48	-167.90
Methyl Benzoate $E_a = 67.01$ kJ mol ⁻¹					
309.5	1.083	8615	64.488	109.290	-127.84
313.5	2.506	8650	64.405	104.542	-128.02
328.0	7.942	8717	64.284	106.354	-128.26

energy for methyl benzoate may be due to the precipitation of benzoic acid over zinc oxide.

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Conductometric Study of Interaction of Sodium *N*-Chlorobenzenesulphonamide with Silver(I), Mercury(II), Thorium(IV) and Zirconium(IV) Solutions**

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IN continuation of our work on organic haloamines¹⁻³, we report in this note the result of our studies on the reactions of chloramine-B with some metal ions.

Experimental

Silver nitrate, mercuric chloride, thorium chloride, thorium nitrate, zirconium oxychloride and zirconium nitrate were of AR grade and their solutions were prepared in triply distilled water. Aqueous solutions of chloramine-B¹ were standardized by the iodometric method. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Conductance measurements were made at room temperature (27°) using a Phillips PR 9500 conductivity bridge with a dip type conductivity cell (cell constant : 0.66 cm⁻¹). Potentiometric titrations were carried out on an Elico model LI-120 digital pH meter.

Uv spectra were obtained on a Beckmann DB spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Carl-Zeiss UR-10 spectrophotometer.

The white precipitates obtained by the addition of chloramine-B (CAB) to silver nitrate and mercuric chloride solutions were filtered, washed repeatedly with water, dried and analysed. The compound of Ag^I analysed for C₆H₅SO₂NClAg (Found : Ag, 36.26 ; Cl, 11.73 ; S, 10.89 ; N, 4.65. Requires Ag, 36.18 ; Cl, 11.90 ; S, 10.72 ; N, 4.69%). The compound of Hg^{II} analysed for (C₆H₅SO₂NCl)₂Hg (Found : Hg, 34.82 ; Cl, 12.48 ; S, 11.1 ; N, 4.85. Requires Hg, 34.5 ; Cl, 12.20 ; S, 11.01 ; N, 4.82%). Silver compound decomposed at 155-160° and mercury compound at 140°. Aqueous solutions of both the compounds liberate iodine from acidified potassium iodide solution.

The compound obtained by the addition of a solution of Th^{IV} or Zr^{IV} to a solution of CAB was filtered, washed with water and was estimated iodometrically in glacial acetic acid medium. The unreacted CAB in the filtrate was also determined iodometrically. The amount of H⁺ reacted was calculated by titration against NaOH. It is found that CAB and H⁺ reacted approximately in 1 : 1 molar ratio and the amount of product formed is nearly half the amount of CAB reacted. The solid

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